

Centre[4] Art and Research Services: Researchers with an Interest in the Arts

Abstract

This table is intended for those who identify somewhere within the following:

- Researchers who are interested in partnering with artists, and/or
- Researchers who are interested in integrating art into their research practice/project.

If you are considering working with Centre[4] Art and Research (C[4]), we can set up a meeting to hear a bit about your project or practice and to talk about the services that C[4] can provide. C[4] offers different levels of support/facilitation and an accompanying fee structure.

Administrative Details

Authors: Paton, C., Bernier, A., Sinding, C., Maxwell, C., Sproule, S. & Sas van der Linden, L.

Affiliation: McMaster University, Centre[3] for Artistic and Social Practice; Centre[4] Art and Research; McMaster University Community Research Platform

Published: January 2024

Contact: patoncj@mcmaster.ca

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10592286>

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Service	Description	Fee
<p>Consultation A: Exploring and Clarifying the project</p>	<p>Consultation: C[4] will meet with you to think through and/or hear about the role research plays in the project or practice. Here are some examples of questions we might ask:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What does research mean in the context of your project? • What does art mean in the context of your project? • What are you hoping engagement with research would do for/with your project? • What are you hoping engagement with art would do for/with your project? <p>Connection: Connecting to artists whose art practice could align with the researcher’s initial project.</p> <p>C[4] will explain the hoped-for project and collaboration to a few artists who might be a good fit and where there seems promise on both sides. We will facilitate a meeting to talk through the potential collaboration.</p> <p>Connection might also include outreach via C[4], Centre[3] for Artistic + Social Practice, and McMaster University Community Research Platform (CRP) websites. C[4] and CRP staff may also provide connections via personal knowledge.</p>	<p>Consultation A is a free service. Along with the consultation, it also includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direction to C[4] tools and resources, • Relevant project examples, • Referrals to funding sources, and • Preliminary discussion of potential roles for C[4] in your project.
<p>After Consultation A, you may decide one of many paths to move forward. This could include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) not continuing with the project; b) continuing the project without support of C[4]; c) continuing the project with the initial support of C[4], such as that offered in Consultation B. 		

<p>Consultation B: What is the role of the artist in collaboration with the researcher?</p>	<p>Consultation: Part of the consultation involves figuring out what the role of the artist will be within a project. The following are a few options that we've identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artist as lead – driving the direction of research, • Artist as co-investigator, • Artist as consultant – offer professional services as expert in their art practice and potentially theory, • Artist delivers arts programming as a way of generating data/stories/insight, • Artist involved in analysis of research data/ stories, • Artist involved in designing and creating knowledge exchange from research, and/or • Artist provides knowledge sharing once research completed. <p>(Please see our “Artist Role Frameworks” document for further discussion of these roles).</p>	<p>Consultation B, as well as all further consultations and work with Centre[4], will have a fee attached.</p> <p>The fee for services will be determined on a case-by-case basis.</p>
	<p>Examples: Providing relevant examples.</p> <p>Once we have clarified where art fits within your project, C[4] will provide some examples of research projects that have integrated art.</p> <p>C[4] will do our best to provide examples of projects that are either close to your field of research or that involve art in the way that you are envisioning/beginning to envision.</p>	
	<p>Resources: Providing resources to support equitable partnerships (resources are free and available on the C[4] website).</p> <p>Here is a list of the written resources C[4] provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of services in action • Partnership agreement guidelines 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Arts output, process, and data sharing agreement ● Fee structure guideline ● Ethical considerations when engaging with the arts guideline ● Collaborative partnership checklist ● Sample workshop templates for arts involved research practices 	
<p>After Consultation B, you may decide to move forward with or without the support of C[4]. Your project might involve:</p> <p>a) continuing the project without support of C[4];</p> <p>b) continuing the project with C[4] continued facilitation as in Consultation C.</p>		
<p>Consultation C: Ongoing Consultation, Reflection, and Documentation process</p>	<p>Consultation: As the project as well as the relationships involved, shift and grow, C[4] may be able to provide ongoing consultation/check-ins regarding partnerships. This includes checking in about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Roles and expectations, ● Budgets, ● Collaboration agreements, ● Ethical concerns and considerations ● Other needs/concerns that arise within the project. <p>Ongoing consultation also involves working with you to develop a plan for ongoing documentation of your project or practice.</p> <p>*see note regarding documentation process</p>	<p>Consultation C will have a fee attached.</p> <p>The fee for services will be determined on a case-by-case basis.</p>
	<p>Follow-Up: Reflecting on the process.</p> <p>Once your project is finished, C[4] will provide follow up/offer reflection on how the project went. Some questions we might ask are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How did this project go? ● What's next? ● What kind of support could you use more or less of? 	

*Something we've noticed in developing this work is that if documentation of a project is left until the end, it tends to land in the academic and/or less artistic realm. For example, academic articles and reports often provide much of the public facing information about a project. We want to encourage and support creative, ongoing processes of documentation, so that the *process* of the project can also be made visible and potentially celebrated!